

MECHANISM OF DROUGHT TOLERANCE IN PLANT AND ITS MANAGEMENT THROUGH DIFFERENT METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Control of drought stress in plant is not only very complex, but is also highly influenced by other environmental factors and by the developmental stage of the plant. Here we review certain physiological responses of plants to a deficit of water include leaf wilting, a reduction in leaf area, leaf abscission, and thereby reducing water loss through transpiration, and increasing the rate of photosynthesis in relation to drought. Critical global scenarios related to water availability for human consumption and crop production anticipated to arise in the near future, and intensive research is currently being conducted on basic and applied issues, from molecular to ecological approaches. Considering that up to 70-80% of the fresh water is utilized for irrigation of field crops, development of plants with less water requirements can contribute much to alleviate the problem of excessive water consumption in agriculture. These responses improve the water-use efficiency of the plant on the short term and we can also improve the resistance in plant against certain stress by genetic manipulation for increased drought tolerance in plants, developing drought tolerant plants by traditional breeding and transgenic approaches.

KEYWORDS: Drought stress; photosynthesis; physiological responses; respiration; tolerances mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Although some of the effects of a rapidly imposed water deficit might be common to those when the deficit is imposed slowly, reproduction of slowly imposed water deficits under field conditions is required when considering a crop's response to drought. This type of study will allow the evaluation of acclimation processes in mature plants as well as plant resistance to a multistress situation that often is the cause of dramatic losses in agricultural production. Recent studies revealed that molecular and metabolic responses of plants to a combination of stresses are unique and cannot be extrapolated from the separate study of individual stresses (Mittler, 2006). Moreover, from an agricultural perspective, drought is ultimately defined in terms of its effects on yield, since this is the relevant issue when addressing the improvement of crop production under water-limited environments. Consequently, the timing of water deficits during the season (e.g. sowing, crop establishment, flowering, or grain filling) may have a much larger impact on yield than the intensity of drought (Aranjuelo *et al.*, (2011), Pinheiro and Chaves (2011)).

Adaptation to drought is undoubtedly one of the most complex biological processes. It involves numerous changes including reduced growth, transcriptional activation/inactivation of specific genes, transient increases in ABA levels, accumulation of compatible solutes and protective enzymes, increased levels of antioxidants and suppression of energy-consuming pathways.

Drought reduces plant productivity by inhibiting growth and photosynthesis (Taiz, *et al.*, 1998). A positive correlation between photosynthesis rate and crop yield is commonly found (Pooter and Remkes, 1990), but factors changing assimilate partitioning and utilization can reduce this association (Guo *et al.*, 2002). Alteration of growth patterns in plants contributes to survival under water depletion conditions. An increase in root to shoot ratio is found commonly in physiological studies on the effects of drought on plants. Growth arrest can be considered as a medium by which plants can preserve carbohydrates for sustained metabolism, prolong energy supply and recovery faster after stress relief. On the other hand, continuation of root growth increases the exploratory capacity of plants in deeper more humid soil layers. Reduction of photosynthesis under restricted

water supply is caused by stomatal and metabolic effects. Which factor is more important for this reduction has a matter of intense debate since the earliest reports on the effects of drought on photosynthesis (Medrano *et al.*, 2002). Water deficit produces stomatal closure and thereby decreases intercellular CO₂ concentrations, whereas dehydration of the mesophyll cells damages the photosynthetic apparatus. Under conditions in which photosynthesis is impaired and chloroplasts are exposed to excess excitation energy, there is a photoreduction of oxygen that results in a concomitant production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), the superoxide anion, and hydroxyl radicals (Inzé and Van, 1995), which in turn damage membranes and enzymes. In this regard, it is considered that photosystem II (PSII) is more sensitive to drought stress than photosystem I (Durães *et al.*, 2001). Although major ROS production induced by hyperosmotic stress occurs at intracellular sites, it was also shown that a cell wall diamine oxidase (Lin and Kao, 2002) and a plasma membrane NADPH oxidase (Jian and Zhang, 2002) were activated by drought, respectively.

Drought is the most significant limiting factor for plant agriculture worldwide, which can cause serious losses of yields and productivity in most crop plants in arid and sub-arid regions. The degree of these effects depends on its impact on the plant physiological, biochemical, as well as molecular biological process and the ability of plant to adapt to drought stress (Bulbotko, 1973; Atkinson *et al.*, 2000; Massonnet *et al.*, 2007). The major environmental factor that constrains the productivity and stability of plants is water stress (Araus *et al.*, 2002). According to the different scenarios predicted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Alley *et al.*, 2007) it is expected that there will be a reduction in precipitation and rising evapotranspiration rates. The perceived need to gain further understanding of photosynthesis, so as to alleviate practical problems such as crop yield under drought conditions, has increased interest in 'water stress physiology' (Lawlor and Tezara, 2009). Photosynthesis and cell growth are among the primary processes to be affected by drought (Chaves and Oliveira, 2004; Chaves *et al.*, 2009). Under drought conditions deficiency of water in plant tissues may lead to stomatal closure resulting in lower CO₂ intake and ultimately photosynthesis will be adversely affected (Lawlor and Cornic, 2002; Lawlor and Tezara, 2009; Chaves *et al.*, 2009). Although it is generally accepted that stomatal closure is the main factor limiting photosynthetic activity under moderate water-limiting conditions (Chaves *et al.*, 2002, 2003), when water stress is more severe, metabolic impairment takes place (Medrano *et al.*, 2002). Deleterious effects of drought on photosynthesis will be mediated by the responsiveness of (i) the respiration system, electron transport, and ATP synthesis in the mitochondria (Atkin and Macherel, 2009), (ii) the accumulation of stress metabolites (Zhang *et al.*, 1999), and (iii) gene expression and protein synthesis (Lawlor and Tezara, 2009).

Often the studies of molecular responses of plants to drought use very artificial systems of stress imposition, such as an instantaneous decline in water availability produced by detaching organs or removing the plants from substrates.

Such experimental conditions cannot provide information on relevant acclimation processes that might occur under field conditions. Furthermore, rapid alterations (within hours) would not necessarily reflect a response to a long-term water shortage but instead a short-term adjustment to a new environmental condition.

As the key process of primary metabolism, photosynthesis plays a central role in plant performance under drought (see reviews by Chaves *et al.*, 2003, 2009; Flexas *et al.*, 2004; Lawlor and Tezara, 2009). The decline observed in leaf net carbon uptake as a result of plant water deficits is followed by an alteration in partitioning of the photoassimilates at the whole plant level, corresponding in general to an increase in the root to shoot ratio. This is the result of the decline in shoot growth and the maintenance of root growth under decreasing water in the soil (Sharp, 2002). Such a response is mediated by hormonal control, namely by abscisic acid (ABA), ethylene, and their interactions (Wilkinson and Davies, 2010).

Response of crop photosynthesis to drought, it is relevant to approach it at the canopy scale as well, since crop productivity is dependent on photoassimilates produced at the whole plant level. It is known that the decline in stomatal aperture is accompanied by the adjustment of leaf area at the whole plant level. It occurs either via the inhibition of new leaf growth or via the earlier senescence of older leaves, in the case of prolonged stress. This reduction in foliage dimension leads to decreased transpirational area but also to lower intercepted radiation throughout the growing season and ultimately to decreased biomass production (Pereira and Chaves, 1993). In many crops, alteration of the leaf angle with dehydration, towards smaller angles, will also diminish total intercepted radiation and therefore carbon assimilation by the plant, but will have an important protective role against excess solar. Photosynthetic resilience to drought is known to vary with leaf age (Chaves, 1991).

Younger leaves tend to be more resistant to drought than older leaves, and this increased tolerance may be particularly relevant in plants where a severe reduction in the size of the leaf canopy occurs as a result of shedding of older leaves, because it allows a fast recovery following rehydration (Pereira and Chaves, 1993). In addition to a plant's ability to avoid and/or endure water stress, photosynthetic recovery following rehydration is pivotal to dictate a plant's resistance to drought and to prevent dramatic declines in crop yield (Chaves *et al.*, 2009). It was shown that recovery from a severe stress was a two stage process: the first stage occurs during the first hours or days upon re-watering, corresponding to the improvement of leaf water status and stomatal re-opening (Pinheiro *et al.*, 2005; Antˆnio *et al.*, 2008; Hayano-Kanashiro *et al.*, 2009); and the second stage lasts several days and requires de novo synthesis of photosynthetic proteins (Kirschbaum, 1988). Previous stress intensity and/or duration are crucial factors affecting both the velocity and the extent of recovery of photosynthesis (Miyashita *et al.*, 2005; Flexas *et al.*, 2006a). Long-term down-regulation of *gs* after re-watering may be derived from limited recovery of leaf-specific hydraulic conductivity (Galme's *et al.*, 2007c). From the molecular point of view, the comparison between susceptible and tolerant genotypes suggests that drought tolerance is associated with a rapid modulation of genes from different TF gene families during recovery. For example, the greatest difference between drought-tolerant and drought-sensitive maize genotypes was observed in the speed of transcriptional down-regulation during recovery from drought (Hayano-Kanashiro *et al.*, 2009).

The respiration connection: support for Photosynthesis recovery Net carbon gain that ultimately dictates plant growth and development reflects the balance between photosynthesis and respiration (in auto- and heterotrophic tissues). Indeed, 30–70% of the CO₂ fixed per day by net photosynthesis in well-watered plants is released back into the atmosphere by plant respiration, the larger part through the leaves (Aktin and Macherel, 2009). The impact of water deficits on dark respiration is still far from clear, with reports in the literature comprising decreases, maintenance, or increases in the rates of this process (Gimeno *et al.*, 2010). Inhibition of respiration under drought has been observed in actively growing roots and mature leaves of crops and herbaceous species (Ribas-Carbo *et al.*, 2005; Galmes *et al.*, 2007b). Decreased availability of the substrate to the mitochondria under conditions of low photosynthesis as well as inhibition of leaf growth may explain reduced respiration, mostly in its growth component (Flexas *et al.*, 2006a; Gimeno *et al.*, 2010). However, a higher demand for respiratory ATP under severe water stress (to compensate for the lowered ATP production in the chloroplasts) may be required to support photosynthesis repair mechanisms, as suggested by Flexas *et al.* (2005, 2006a) and Atkin and Macherel (2009). Higher respiration rates, mainly as the maintenance component, are then observed in droughted plants, underlying acclimation mechanisms of drought (Gratani *et al.*, 2007; Slot *et al.*, 2008). Finally, a third response pattern, with no alterations in the rates of dark respiration under drought, was reported in several species, mostly in evergreen perennials (Galmes *et al.*, 2007b; Gimeno *et al.*, 2010).

Elaborating on such contrasting results, Atkin and Macherel (2009) proposed a model where mitochondrial respiration dictates plant survival and rapid recovery of productivity under water stress conditions, by ensuring survival under extended periods of drought. According to some authors (Gimeno *et al.*, 2010), shrubs and trees that possess long-lived leaves are likely to show slower responses to drought than short-lived species that need to optimize their carbon gain over shorter periods and therefore may respond quickly to water scarcity, lowering their respiration rates. From the biochemical point of view it has been reported that the electron partitioning towards the alternative respiration pathway sharply increases under severe drought, even when total respiration rates are not greatly affected (Ribas-Carbo *et al.*, 2005). Unlike many other stresses, water stress does not affect the quantity of mitochondrial alternative oxidase protein, suggesting that a biochemical regulation causes this mitochondrial electron shift. This may have a physiological significance, since evidence is accumulating to support a role for the alternative oxidase in the prevention of the formation of ROS (Lambers *et al.*, 2005). Overall, the changes observed in respiration in response to drought are smaller as compared with the large decreases in photosynthesis; therefore, as carbon uptake becomes more limiting under water scarcity, respiration increases proportionally, leading to increased leaf intercellular CO₂ and altered plant carbon balance (Lawlor and Tezara, 2009). As already mentioned, the ratio between the respiratory needs for growth and maintenance will also change in plants under water stress, the component devoted to shoot growth being drastically decreased (Flexas *et al.*, 2006a).

Drought and photosynthesis: the metabolic connections

Although impressive advances have been made in the last decade with respect to the nature of events occurring in plants subjected to drought, an integrative picture of the metabolic regulation taking place is still missing (Rolland *et al.*, 2006; Shinozaki *et al.*, 2007). This is partly related to the disparate experimental conditions of the studies being done and the very artificial conditions of the applied stress, frequently acute and/or too severe.

Moreover, in many studies, particularly those dealing with the molecular responses to drought, plant water status, leaf conductance, and photosynthetic rate are usually not measured, which makes comparative analysis of these data very difficult to perform. Details

Fig. 1. Biological networks generated for drought and photosynthesis interactions considering the literature available (1995 to February,2010)

on regulatory mechanisms and interactions are available for specific situations, although systematic information on common/general effects is still scarce as shown in fig.1. It is compelling that the vast amount of information on plant transcriptomes under drought has not yet been translated into genotype selection. This is for the most part due to low correlations between transcript abundance and corresponding protein and enzyme activities, as well as plant physiological performance, the question ‘what do these genes contribute to stress tolerance?’ still being largely unanswered (Chaves *et al.*, 2009; Deyholos, 2010). New experimental and computational methods are starting to allow multilevel analysis that can integrate physiological, transcriptome, proteome, and metabolome data, thus providing a more detailed view of the cellular events (Eberhard *et al.*, 2008), and contributing to disclosure of the existence of common metabolic features in photosynthetic responses to drought.

Effects at the transcriptional level:

(ii) drought, photosynthesis, and strongly associated pathways

Effect of drought at the gene level in the model plant *Arabidopsis* and the crop plants rice and barley for the genes/proteins represented in Fig. 1B. The main findings may be summarized as follows. (i) The stress imposition method (soil versus paper) significantly affects the responses. The principal component analysis bi-plot generated with the *Arabidopsis* arrays shows that the soil data sets group together, while paper data sets are more dispersed and not mixed with the soil experiments (data not shown). (ii) In the same data set, distinct effects are observed within the same gene family, which allows the hypothesis that at the protein level the effects can be cancelled out. Furthermore, protein activity is modulated at many levels including post-translational modifications (see Eberhard *et al.*, 2008), with activity being modulated via substrate flux and availability and cellular compartmentation (Deyholos, 2010). (iii) The drought effect in a given gene is highly variable, with few exceptions (notably ABI1 and ABI3). (iv) Usually the observed responses (up- or down-regulation) are not reversed with stress progression.

The present meta-analysis (Fig. 1), taken together with the transcriptomic data, highlights the difficulties faced when searching for metabolic events associated with stress and in gaining insight into the relevant pathways,

because not all biological and methodological variables are considered in the different experiments. Although the association of a given response with stress perception, intensity, tolerance, or sensitivity is still rare, the analysis allowed recognition of some potentially relevant features. For example, ABI1 is up-regulated under water deficits in both Arabidopsis and barley plant systems and stress types, while for ABI3 the opposite trend is observed. ETR1 showed a similar response to ABI1, although not so marked, and seems not to respond to acute stress. These genes are related to stomatal closure regulation and provide a link between several hormone pathways. Recently, Khandelwal *et al.* (2010) highlighted a new target for ABI3 action in *Physcomitrella patens* (in an acute stress experiment). They inferred that several transcripts produced during ABA pre-treatment (necessary for *P. patens* desiccation survival) are necessary for recovery (ABI3 mutants do not survive). This may be linked with previous findings of gene expression required for stress recovery being already operative during desiccation (Bray, 1993). Accordingly, very few rehydration-specific proteins are known (Bartels and Salamini, 2001), and in the leaves of two resurrection plants (*Xerophyta humilis* and *Craterostigma wilmsii*) recovery is largely independent on de novo gene transcription and protein translation (Dace *et al.*, 1998; Cooper and Farrant, 2002). In lupins (Pinheiro *et al.*, 2005) and wheatgrass (Gazanchian *et al.*, 2007), it became apparent that the proteins needed for early plant recovery could already be present during the severe stress phase. Regarding the invertase multigenic family, for three genes (one coding for cell wall invertase and two for neutral invertases) it was possible to distinguish the effects from acute (paper) stress and soil stress experiments. The genes AT3G13970 (cell wall invertases) and AT4G09510 (neutral invertase) are down-regulated under soil water but up-regulated with acute stress; the gene AT3G06500 (neutral invertase) is up-regulated in both systems but it seems to be affected more at the very early stages of the acute stress (1–2 h). This is an example of differences in plant response to the velocity of stress imposition—sucrose metabolism will be affected in distinct ways when plants acclimate to slowly imposed water or with a fast response to a dramatic change in tissue water status. Moreover, the light regime under which plants are grown may also drastically influence the results. For example, when water deficits were imposed on plants adapted to low light, as in a recent study with Arabidopsis (180 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), the expression of a set of sugar-responsive genes indicates increased, rather than decreased, carbon availability (Hummel *et al.*, 2010). Indeed, under such conditions photosynthesis was not affected under severe stress (because it was light limited) and the concomitant inhibition of shoot growth gave rise to a surplus of carbon, which was redirected to root growth. It must be emphasized that these results cannot be extrapolated to field conditions where net carbon uptake will be decreased and carbon limitation will be apparent.

Signals and metabolic cross-talk

In the chain of events triggered by drought, one relevant issue relates to signals and signaling cascades and their interactions. Although these terms (signals and signaling cascades) are often used, the biological rationale and supportive data are not always obvious. Some questions remain elusive. Are the observed effects a signal or a consequence of the stimulus (direct or indirect)? How do such changes lead to metabolic rearrangements in photosynthesis? Hormones Water deficit affects biosynthesis, accumulation, and redistribution of major plant hormones, with ABA (synthesized either in leaves or in roots) playing the major role in controlling stomatal aperture and therefore photosynthetic carbon uptake under conditions of water scarcity (Dodd, 2003; Hirayama and Shinozaki, 2007). Stomatal sensitivity to ABA is modulated by a number of external drivers, such as temperature, ozone, nitrogen nutrition (often altered in drying soil), and endogenous components, including cytosolic pH or hydraulic signals that can either reinforce or moderate ABA-based signals (Wilkinson and Davies, 2002, 2010; Parent *et al.*, 2009). Recent reports show that stomatal function is also dependent on other hormones (auxin, cytokinin, ethylene, brassinosteroids, jasmonates, and salicylic acid) and on the degree of their interactions (see the reviews by Acharya and Assmann, 2009; Wilkinson and Davies, 2010). In general, auxin, cytokinin, or ethylene tends to inhibit ABA-mediated stomatal closure, whereas brassinosteroids, jasmonates, and salicylic acid display a concurrent action with ABA. Moreover, all these hormones modulate the expression of different drought related genes (Shinozaki and Yamaguchi-Shinozaki, 2007; Huang *et al.*, 2008). Multiple cascades of cellular biochemical events have also been associated with the regulation of stomatal guard cells, such as the activation of G-proteins, the production of ROS (ABA stimulated) and NO, cytosolic Ca²⁺, protein phosphorylation/dephosphorylation, and reorganization of the cytoskeleton (Acharya and Assmann, 2009). The phosphatases ABI1 and ABI2 were shown to be crucial for ABA-mediated stomatal regulation (Merlot *et al.*, 2001) and are one of the strong connection points in photosynthesis responses to drought ABI1 in Fig. 1B. Still, many questions remain to be clarified, namely the molecular basis of cross-talk among different hormones or the underlying causes for dual roles played by some of them, such as ethylene or even ABA, as recognized by Parent *et al.* (2009). Recent attention was given to the interactions observed between hormonal and circadian networks, since it has been demonstrated that a large proportion of transcripts involved in hormonal metabolism, catabolism, and signaling are also regulated by the circadian clock (Dodd *et al.*, 2007; Robertson *et al.*, 2009). Daily rhythms have been recognized for a long time in different plant processes, namely photosynthesis and stomatal aperture, and this may have resulted from an evolutionary pressure in order to prevent physiological responses that might be counterproductive during some parts of the day, when temperature and radiation are

excessive. Circadian clocks may therefore moderate or produce antagonistic effects relative to hormones, such as those they produce with sugars, as is highlighted further on.

Redox signals

Maintaining homeostasis of redox and adenylate systems is essential for cell functioning. Whenever an imbalance develops between capture of light and its utilization via CO₂ and NO₃ – reduction, as may happen under drought, redox signals from photosynthetic electron transport and production of ROS may occur (Lawlor, 2009) (see Fig. 1). It has now been extensively demonstrated in several biological systems that these redox signals and ROS have an important function in the plant's acclimation to stress (Buchanan and Balmer, 2005; Hayano-Kanashiro *et al.*, 2009). ROS are produced in plant tissues due to the partial reduction of oxygen as, for example, in the photosynthetic and the respiratory electron chains or the photorespiration pathway, or they accumulate as a result of the activity of peroxidases, membrane-located NADPH oxidases, etc., and this production increases dramatically under environmental stress (Mittler *et al.*, 2004). On the other hand, the intensity, duration, and localization of the different ROS signals are determined by the interplay between the ROS-producing and ROS-scavenging pathways of the cell, as highlighted in Fig. 1B (nitrate reductase and catalase). Further, antioxidants such as ascorbate, tocopherol, or glutathione (Fig. 1A; Supplementary Tables S1, S2 at JXB online) are able to control the lifetime of ROS signals and therefore participate in the overall redox regulation that ultimately controls the energy balance in plants (Foyer and Noctor, 2009). Although ROS can modulate many pathways (e.g. mitogen-activated protein kinase cascades) and influence the activity of TFs, redox control over photosynthesis is still largely unknown. It may occur, at least partly, through the monitoring of the cell redox status by several molecules in different cellular compartments, reporting the functional state of the chloroplast to the nucleus (Pfannschmidt *et al.*, 2009), as suggested by Jaspers and Kangasjarvi (2010), since ROS are mostly ephemeral molecules.

Plant Drought Tolerance Mechanisms

Plants respond to their changing environment in a complex, integrated way that allows them to react to the specific set of conditions and constraints present at a given time. Therefore, the genetic control of tolerance to abiotic stresses is not only very complex, but is also highly influenced by other environmental factors and by the developmental stage of the plant. The physiological responses of plants to a deficit of water include leaf wilting, a reduction in leaf area, leaf abscission, and the stimulation of root growth by directing nutrients to the underground parts of the plants. Plants are more susceptible to drought during flowering and seed development (the reproductive stages), as plant's resources are deviated to support root growth. In addition, abscisic acid (ABA), a plant stress hormone, induces the closure of leaf stomata (microscopic pores involved in gas exchange), thereby reducing water loss through transpiration, and decreasing the rate of photosynthesis. These responses improve the water-use efficiency of the plant on the short term. Plant cells are required to maintain water balance. To maintain this water balance, plants absorb water when water potential is negative. Cells can decrease their water potential through the accumulation of solutes, such as sugars, amino acids, organic acids and ions – especially potassium (K⁺). As cellular enzymes are severely inhibited by the presence of ions, these must be removed from the cytosol (the ground fluid substance of the cell) and stored in special storage cell organelles, the vacuoles. Compatible solutes that accumulate in the cytosol and do not interfere with enzymatic reactions comprise sugar alcohols (mannitol and sorbitol), the amino acid proline, and glycine betaine. The synthesis of these compounds by the plant enhances tolerance to drought (Zhang *et al.*, 2004). The plant's response to drought is accompanied by the activation of genes involved in the perception of drought stress and in the transmission of the stress signal. One group are genes that encode proteins that protect the cells from the effects of desiccation. These genes include those that govern the: accumulation of compatible solutes; passive transport across membranes; energy-requiring water transport systems; and protection and stabilization of cell structures from desiccation and damage by reactive oxygen species (Shinozaki *et al.*, 2007). A second group of genes activated by drought is comprised by regulatory proteins that further regulate the transduction of the stress signal and modulate gene expression. At least four independent stress responsive genetic regulatory pathways are known to exist in plants, forming a highly complex and redundant gene network (Umezawa *et al.*, 2006; Shinozaki *et al.*, 2007). Two of the pathways are dependent on the hormone ABA, and two are ABA independent. These pathways are also implicated in the perception and response to additional stress factors, including cold, high temperature, and salinity.

Genetic Engineering Drought Tolerant Plants

Although not a crop plant, *Arabidopsis* has played a vital role in the elucidation of the basic processes underlying stress tolerance, and the knowledge obtained has been transferred to a certain degree to important

food plants (Zhang *et al.*, 2004). Many of the genes known to be involved in stress tolerance have been isolated initially in *Arabidopsis*. The introduction of several stress-inducible genes into plants by genetic engineering has resulted to increased tolerance of transgenics to drought, cold and salinity stresses (Umezawa *et al.*, 2006) and (Shinozaki *et al.*, 2007).

Genetic manipulation of the stress response to abscisic acid (ABA)

ABA levels in the plant greatly increase in response to water stress, resulting in the closure of stomata thereby reducing the level of water loss through transpiration from leaves and activate stress response genes. The reaction is reversible: once water becomes available again, the level of ABA drops, and stomata re-opens. Increasing the plant's sensitivity to ABA has therefore been a very important target for improving drought tolerance. *ERA1*, a gene identified in *Arabidopsis*, encodes the β -subunit of a farnesyl-transferase, and is involved in ABA signaling. Plants lacking *ERA1* activity have increased tolerance to drought, however are also severely compromised in yield. In order to have a conditional, reversible down-regulation of ABA, a group of Canadian researchers used a drought inducible promoter to drive the antisense expression of *ERA1*, in both *Arabidopsis* and canola plants (Wang *et al.*, 2005). Transgenic plants performed significantly better under water stress, with consistently higher yields over conventional varieties.

Importantly, there was no difference in performance between transgenic and controls in conditions of sufficient water, demonstrating that the technology has no yield-drag. Multilocation trials have confirmed yield increases due to enhanced protection to drought to be 15-25% compared to non-transgenic controls (<http://www.performanceplants.com>).

ABA-independent gene regulation to drought stress

The transcription factors *DREB1* and *DREB2* are important in the ABA-independent drought tolerant pathways that induce the expression of stress response genes. Over-expression of the native form of *DREB1*, and of a constitutively active form of *DREB2*, increases the tolerance of transgenic *Arabidopsis* plants to drought, high salinity, and cold. Although these genes were initially identified in *Arabidopsis* plants, their presence and role in stress tolerance have been reported in many other important crops, such as rice, tomato, barley, canola, maize, soybean, rye, wheat and maize, indicating that this is a conserved, universal stress defense mechanism in plants (Shinozaki *et al.*, 2007). This functional conservation makes the *DREB* genes important targets for crop improvement for drought tolerance through genetic engineering.

Developing drought tolerant plants by traditional breeding

In light of critical global scenarios related to water availability for human consumption and crop production anticipated to arise in the near future, intensive research is currently being conducted on basic and applied issues, from molecular to ecological approaches. Considering that up to 70-80% of the fresh water is utilized for irrigation of field crops (CEAG, 2001), development of plants with less water requirements can contribute much to alleviate the problem of excessive water consumption in agriculture.

Because of the existence of ample natural variability among organisms for both biotic and abiotic tolerance, the existence of genes that control the response of plants to environmental stress has been long accepted. In fact, genetic resistance to many biotic stresses has been demonstrated to be the result of single (Mendelian) genes. Classical breeding approaches have demonstrated, on the other hand, that traits conferring stress tolerance are controlled by a great variety of genes acting additive and synergistically (Dvorak, 1994 and Frova, 1999), which makes genetic manipulation of plants for increased drought tolerance a difficult task. Conventional breeding methods based on crosses and selection schemes have made some contributions towards stress-tolerance crop improvement (Acevedo, and Fereres, 1993), though attempts to generate plant varieties with improved salinity or drought tolerance using this approach have proved largely unsuccessful (Flower and Yeo, 1995). Although it may be possible to improve abiotic stress tolerance using whole plant phenotypic or physiological strategies and pyramiding breeding schemes, such approaches, even those based on marker-assisted selection, are costly, slow, require massive screening labors to identify specific quantitative traits, while linkage of agronomically important QTL's to undesirable traits can sometimes occur. For example, selection for glycine betaine content could result in increased incidence of some insects (Araya, et al., 1991) and microbial diseases such as *Fusarium* (Pearce et al., 1976). It is expected that selection supported on genetic molecular markers help resolving some drawbacks of the conventional breeding methods.

Meanwhile, efforts to engineer improved tolerance using single or multigene transfer of genes by genetic transformation offer far more rapid and promising improvements in stress tolerance (Cushman, 2001).

Genetic manipulation for increased drought tolerance in plants

Because of the occurrence of common responses (e.g. increased production of compatible solutes) to drought and salinity, some authors have proposed that these two factors can be treated simultaneously (Bray,1997), even though some caution should be taken into account because some injuries are stress-specific. For example, the toxicity caused by sodium deserves to be treated separately (Zhang et al.,2000). Plant response to drought stress has been analyzed at the ecological, cellular, physiological, and molecular levels. The knowledge gained by studies in these research areas have settled the technological basis now utilized for increasing the drought tolerance of plants by genetic manipulation. The limiting factor is the availability of structural genes and regulatory elements directly involved in tolerance to drought stress. If molecular biology is to really contribute to improvement of water stress tolerance of plants a logical framework for revealing basic parameters of stress tolerance should be followed. Firstly, water stress responsive genes can be identified by means of all the expression analysis techniques now available. Latter, isolation of these genes can be accomplished by differential hybridization techniques and their function evaluated in transgenic plants using model species as receptor organisms. Transgenic crop performance can be finally evaluated under field conditions or the identified genes used for marker-assisted selection (MAS). Research designed to identify, characterize, and determine the function of genes and their products that are directly involved in the ability of certain plants to survive and fully recover from desiccation is currently underway. The hypothesis subjacent to much work on genetic improvement of stress tolerance that at least part of the genetic background required for tolerance is also present in non-tolerant plants is supported by the observation that gradual acclimation of sensitive plants or plant cells leads to acquisition of certain degree of tolerance (Zhu, 2001). However, it is clear the existence of highly specific and specialized genes in some tolerant plants (Bartels, D. and Salamini, F. 2001). Because some stress relevant genes are ubiquitously present in the plant kingdom, an alternative hypothesis is proposed that stress tolerance is more the result of global expression patterns than of genome composition (Bartels and Sunkar, 2005). Another assumption in molecular work related to stress tolerance has been that an osmotic-stress regulated gene is important to the ability of a plant to adapt to osmotic stress. The other point of view is that not necessarily genes expressed in response to a particular stress are involved in adaptive mechanisms permitting an organism to tolerate the osmotic stress condition.

Although these notions have not been proved or disapproved, there is now a general realization that function of genes should be appropriately tested for conferring them a real participation in drought tolerance of plants (Bray, 1993). From the achievements reached in molecular work we have learnt for example that many osmotic responsive genes are part of a more general stress response system because many osmotic responsive genes also respond to other environmental factors. Thus, it has been realized a lack of specificity in plant responses to stress, as demonstrated by the osmotic induction of heat shock proteins, antioxidative damage enzymes, antifungal proteins and inhibitors of insect digestion (Ingram and Bartels,1996) Although modern and high throughput technologies such as expression profile analysis by DNA microarray technology and analysis of protein profiles by one- and two-dimensional gel electrophoresis are permitting us to know the genes (and proteins) that are up-regulated, down-regulated or newly expressed in response to stress, and in consequence determining those which are central to drought tolerance and genes that are unique to particular strategies for water deficit tolerance, the function of only a limited number of genes products have been established (Bartels and Sunkar, 2005). Because some traits conferring drought tolerance can be, at least theoretically, altered by manipulation of single enzymatic reactions, such as those implicated in osmotic adjustment, it has been theorized on the possibility of generating plants tolerant to water stress by transferring, through genetic transformation technology, only one or a few genes (McCue and Hanson, 1990). The isolation of single genes and the possibility of testing these genes in a new genetic context can be achieved by gene scrutiny, recombination and transformation technologies currently available.

Current strategies for developing drought tolerant plants by transgenic approaches

Part of the possibility of generating drought tolerant plants by means of the transference of only one or few genes derives from the fact that, in order to reduce the impact of the water stress, some plants accumulate certain compounds known as compatible solutes, osmolytes or osmoregulators, and that the alteration or incorporation of the routes conducive to their biosynthesis might redound in an increased tolerance to water deficit. By the knowledge gained through analysis of the perception and transduction modules, it was clear from the commencement of genetic manipulation of plants for increased stress tolerance the convenience of manipulating

a “master” pleiotropic gene with multiple effects on the plant response to stress (Serrano et al., 1999). This “master” gene would be located upstream of the response module. However, current strategies for improving tolerance of sodium stress rely primarily on the production of relative low molecular mass (*Low-Mr*) solutes and on enhancing radical-scavenging enzymes systems (Bohnert and Shen, 1999). From recent reviews concerning the performance of transgenic plants developed for increased drought stress, it is evident that every aspect of the perception-transduction-response modules has been approached. In this regard, it is very interesting to note that practically all adopted manipulating strategies resulted in improved performance of the transformants. However, it is also important to highlight that most of these studies were conducted under laboratory or greenhouse conditions. Therefore, it is evident the urgency of testing these modified crops under field conditions. In addition, the importance of collaborative research between laboratories in different areas (physiology, biochemistry, ecology, and functional genomics) is emphasized, because contradictory results have sometimes been obtained (Blum et al., 1996). These situations would prevent harvesting the fruits of this technology in benefit of the farmers. As with other transgenic organisms, some aspects of genetic manipulation for increased tolerance of plants should be taken into account. It has consistently been found that individual transformants to a unique construct show extensive variability in expression levels, unusual developmental patterns of expression, transgene silencing and occasional phenotypic instability (Peach and Velten, 1991). The molecular basis of this variability has been attributed to “positional effects” or transgene rearrangements that have not been adequately analyzed because the available technological framework have permitted to disregard this situation while identifying the transgenic organisms expressing the transgene in a more “convenient” way. In this connection, the chloroplast transformation technology is expected to solve part of the drawbacks of the nuclear transformation (Koya and Daniell, 2005). The major progress in the field of plant genetic engineering was the transition from the insertion of a single gene to the introduction of multiple genes in a single transformation event. Chloroplast transformation offers the advantage of introducing multiple transgenes in a single transformation event because of the chloroplast’s capacity to transcribe the operons into polycistronic mRNA and translate this mRNA with or without further processing. The high polyploidy of the chloroplast leads to an exceptionally high transcripts levels and accumulation of abundant translated products, up to 46% of total leaf protein (De et al., 2001). Furthermore, the positional effects observed in nuclear transformation are not observed in chloroplast transgenic expression due to site-specific integration of transgenes into the spacer region of the chloroplast genome through homologous recombination. Additionally, it has been observed shown that there is no gene silencing at the transcriptional or translational levels in chloroplast transformation (De et al., 2001). Chloroplasts also offer a medium to compartmentalize toxic foreign proteins, thereby preventing any adverse effects of the gene products (Lee et al., 2003). In most angiosperms, plastid genes are inherited uniparentally in a rigorously maternal fashion. Even supposing transgenic chloroplast could be present in pollen, plastid DNA is eliminated from the male germ line at different points during sperm cell development (Hagemann, 2004). Thus, a minimum risk of transgene dispersion in the nature is achieved through chloroplast transformation. Chloroplast genetic engineering has been applied to improve agronomic traits of plants with successful results in development of insect-resistant plants (McBride, 1995), herbicide resistance (Daniell, 1998), disease-resistant plants (DeGray et al., 2001) and drought (Lee et al., 2003) and salt tolerance (Kumar et al., 2004). Alteration of these latter two traits was approached by increasing the cellular concentration of two important compatible solutes: trehalose and glycine betaine. Finally, If we are to properly manipulate the stress tolerance of plants, it is necessary to increase our knowledge of plant responses at each level of organization, analyzing, for example, the effect of water stress on the photosynthetic behavior of plants and the contribution of stomatal vs. metabolic effects to the reduction in photosynthesis rate and, consequently, in crop productivity (Chang., 1997).

CONCLUSION

Since drought is a common occurrence in many environments, many perennial plant species have developed mechanisms to cope with a restricted water supply. Plants can avoid drought stress by maximizing water uptake (e.g., tapping ground water by deep roots) or minimizing water loss (e.g., stomatal closure, small leaves). Great progress has occurred in recent years in elucidating the nature of the various factors affecting photosynthesis in plants subjected to water deficits. The alterations that do occur in response to stress comprise the restriction of CO₂ diffusion to the chloroplast, as well as metabolic changes, including the modulation of the expression of photosynthesis related genes. However, when trying to make use of publicly available data to establish which events are regulated by and/or regulate photosynthesis, the lack of stress characterization is immediately revealed, impairing the possibility to compare and integrate data. Although significant progress has been made in elucidating the genetic mechanisms underlying drought tolerance, considerable challenges remain. In field conditions, crops are subjected to variable levels of multiple stresses, thus one area of studies that deserves much more attention is the response of plants to a combination of stresses. There, plant’s response to multiple stresses cannot be inferred from the response to individual stress. It is thus essential to test newly developed varieties to multiple stresses, and to carry out extensive field studies in a large range of conditions that assess tolerance as absolute yield increases. Another major challenge is the increasing difficulty and expense in

obtaining approvals for field trials of GM plants. As a number of measures are in place to ensure the safe and responsible design of field tests, excessive precaution should not become a barrier to making sure we use all the tools available to us for a more sustainable agriculture.

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Received for Publication: 12/03/2011

Accepted for Publication: 30/03/2011

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